

PEDAGOGICAL METHODOLOGY AND PEDAGOGICAL SKILLS IN TEACHING ENGLISH TO PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Annotation: *In this article, the methods and skills used by the pedagogue during the lesson to teach the English language to elementary school students quickly, easily, interestingly and clearly.*

Key words: primary classes, innovative technology, interesting games, Bingo

INTRODUCTION

One of the decisions that caused the most fundamental changes in general secondary education is the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" - Resolution No. 1875. Based on this decision, foreign languages will be gradually taught in the form of speaking lessons, and from the 2nd grade, the alphabet, reading and grammar will be taught. According to the decision, under the leadership of the Coordinating Council, which is constantly working on the further development of the study of foreign languages, an unprecedented amount of work was started in all areas of the educational field. For example, since the 2013-2014 academic year, continuous teaching of foreign languages in the form of game-style exercises and oral speech lessons has been launched in the first grades of secondary schools. Also, textbooks and teaching-methodical sets for these classes were created.

It is worth noting that the games in the complexes created for the first grades are proportional to the age of the children. Children began their first acquaintance with a foreign language by learning the culture of greetings, colors and everyday words in the form of a dialogue.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in order to educate mature professionals who have a high level of general professional culture, social activity, independent thinking, and the ability to solve their tasks without difficulty, today our pedagogic teachers use modern and innovative pedagogical technologies. They should understand that it is the main factor of increasing the quality and efficiency of education, and that it is required by the times.

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